

Novel, Symbolic, Differential Spaces of Light: Insights into Cosmology and Special Relativity

by Parker Emmerson, a created being by the grace of Jehovah the Living Allaha.

Abstract: A differential velocity space is defined by:

$$D \left[D \left[D \left[D \left[D \left[\frac{\sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha}, l \right], x \right], r \right], \gamma \right], \theta \right], \alpha \right] - \frac{2 \pi \sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}} = \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 + c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 c^2 r x \gamma \theta + c^2 r^2 \theta^2 + c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2}}$$

where the $l\alpha$, $x\gamma$ and $r\theta$ are arc lengths of arbitrary location, and $\frac{\sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha} = h$, a height extending in corresponding connection to the difference formula: $\theta r = \gamma x - \alpha \sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - h^2}$. The solutions to the resulting equation yield evidence that for such a space, the resulting specific magnitudes are at play. The formula indicates that the difference between the Instantaneous Velocity and the Geometric Mean Velocity is equivalent to the Phenomenological Velocity. Note: The resulting solution to the c variable contains coefficients that are within the ecological scale of human measurements of the, "speed of light," when using material instruments, and these are produced entirely from multiplying coefficient harmonics algebraically and from basically scratch difference formulations. Ordering the difference as above yields such a scaling of the coefficients, while ordering it any other way yields solutions to c that contain coefficients of an extraordinary magnitude, some 10^{175} . Only one of said solutions is delineated below for illustration. This is a piece of observational evidence indicative that we are present in a realm that orders the difference of the meanings of velocities in the a manner of the former solutions, not the latter. The solutions are capable of being graphed and do produce form.

$$\text{In[]:= Solve} \left[\left(\left(- \frac{945 l^3 \alpha^2 (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{16 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{11/2}} + \frac{105 l^3 \alpha^2 \gamma \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \frac{105 l^3 x \alpha^2 \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} \right) \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{105 l^3 \alpha^2 (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
& \frac{105 l^3 \alpha^2 (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta) (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
& \frac{105 l^3 r \alpha^2 \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
& \frac{105 l^3 r x \alpha^2 (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
& \frac{105 l (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{16 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} - \\
& \frac{30 l^3 r x \alpha^2 \gamma \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l^3 \alpha^2 (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
& \frac{15 l^3 \alpha^2 \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l^3 \alpha^2 \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
& \frac{15 l \gamma \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
& \frac{15 l^3 x \alpha^2 (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l x \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
& \frac{15 l (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
& \frac{15 l^3 r \alpha^2 (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
& \frac{15 l (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta) (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
& \frac{15 l r \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l r x (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} + \\
& \frac{3 l^3 \alpha^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \frac{6 l r x \gamma \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \\
& \frac{3 l (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \frac{3 l \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & \frac{3 \text{ l } \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{2 (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \frac{3 \text{ l } x (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{2 (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \\ & \left. \frac{3 \text{ l } r (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{2 (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} - \frac{\text{l}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{3/2}} \right) - \\ & \frac{2 \pi \sqrt{\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}} \Bigg) = \\ & \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 c^2 r x \gamma \theta + c^2 r^2 \theta^2 + c^2 \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}, c \end{aligned}$$

Out[4]= { { c →

$$\begin{aligned} & - \left(\left(1. \sqrt{\left(- \frac{157.914 \text{l}^2 r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{157.914 r x^3 \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{39.4784 \text{l}^4 \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\gamma \theta} + \right. \right. \\ & \frac{78.9568 \text{l}^2 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \theta} - \frac{39.4784 x^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \theta} + \frac{78.9568 \text{l}^2 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \gamma} - \\ & \frac{236.871 r^2 x^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} + \frac{157.914 r^3 x \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \\ & \frac{39.4784 r^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \gamma} - \frac{893025. \text{l}^2 r^2 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\ & \frac{1.07163 \times 10^7 \text{l}^2 r^3 x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\ & \frac{5.89397 \times 10^7 \text{l}^2 r^4 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\ & \frac{1.96466 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 r^5 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^5}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\ & \frac{4.42047 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 r^6 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\ & \frac{7.07276 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 r^7 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^7}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\ & \frac{8.25155 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 r^8 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^8}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\ & \left. \frac{7.07276 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 r^9 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^9}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{4.42047 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{10} \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \theta^{10}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.96466 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{11} \text{ x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta^{11}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{5.89397 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{12} \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{12}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.07163 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{13} \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{13}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{893\,025. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^{14} \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{14}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{198\,450. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{5.1597 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} + \frac{4.08807 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.68683 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} + \frac{4.31629 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x}^9 \gamma^9 \theta^5}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{7.40615 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \text{ x}^8 \gamma^8 \theta^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} + \frac{8.83499 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x}^7 \gamma^7 \theta^7}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{7.40615 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \theta^8}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} + \frac{4.31629 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^9 \text{ x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta^9}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.68683 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{10} \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{10}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} + \frac{4.08807 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{11} \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{11}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{5.1597 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{12} \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{12}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} + \frac{198\,450. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^{13} \text{ x} \gamma \theta^{13}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{11\,025. \text{l}^2 \text{ x}^{12} \gamma^{12}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} + \frac{724\,500. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{9.9162 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} + \frac{5.52069 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^9 \gamma^9 \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.67985 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^8 \gamma^8 \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} + \frac{3.16021 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x}^7 \gamma^7 \theta^5}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{3.8808 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \theta^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} + \frac{3.16021 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta^7}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.67985 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^8}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} + \frac{5.52069 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^9 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^9}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{\phantom{1.67985 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^8}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} + \frac{\phantom{5.52069 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^9 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^9}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{9.9162 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{10} \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{10}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} + \frac{724\,500. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^{11} \text{ x} \gamma \theta^{11}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{11\,025. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^{12} \theta^{12}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^8} - \frac{31\,500. \text{l}^2 \text{ x}^{10} \gamma^{10}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{975\,240. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^9 \gamma^9 \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} - \frac{8.48736 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^8 \gamma^8 \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{3.29944 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^7 \gamma^7 \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} - \frac{7.04075 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{8.99136 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta^5}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} - \frac{7.04075 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{3.29944 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^7}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} - \frac{8.48736 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^8}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{975\,240. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^9 \text{ x} \gamma \theta^9}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} - \frac{31\,500. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^{10} \theta^{10}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{33\,210. \text{l}^2 \text{ x}^8 \gamma^8}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \frac{602\,460. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^7 \gamma^7 \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{3.39863 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \frac{8.70372 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.17487 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \frac{8.70372 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^5}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{3.39863 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \frac{602\,460. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x} \gamma \theta^7}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{33\,210. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \theta^8}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \frac{15\,720. \text{l}^2 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{170\,670. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \frac{583\,320. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{856\,740. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \frac{583\,320. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{170\,670. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x} \gamma \theta^5}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \frac{15\,720. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \theta^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{3201. \text{l}^2 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} + \frac{18\,816. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{32526. \text{l}^2 \text{r}^2 \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} + \frac{18816. \text{l}^2 \text{r}^3 \text{x} \gamma \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{3201. \text{l}^2 \text{r}^4 \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} - \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 \text{r} \text{x}^5 \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{47500.9 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^2 \text{x}^4 \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} - \frac{71251.3 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^3 \text{x}^3 \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{47500.9 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^4 \text{x}^2 \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} - \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^5 \text{x} \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{204. \text{l}^2 \text{x}^2 \gamma^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} + \frac{552. \text{l}^2 \text{r} \times \gamma \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{204. \text{l}^2 \text{r}^2 \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} - \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 \text{r} \text{x}^3 \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{1319.47 \text{l}^3 \text{x}^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} + \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^3 \text{x} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{21111.5 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^2 \text{x}^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} - \frac{1319.47 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{4. \text{l}^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^2} - \frac{1884.96 \text{l}^3 \text{r} \times (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{565.487 \text{l}^3 \text{x}^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^2} + \frac{565.487 \text{l}^3 \text{r}^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{201.062 \text{l} \text{r} \times (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)} + \frac{25.1327 \text{l}^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma \theta (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{50.2655 \text{l} \text{x}^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \theta (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)} + \frac{50.2655 \text{l} \text{r}^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \gamma (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r} \times \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)} + \frac{78.9568 \text{l}^2 \text{r} \times (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{39.4784 \, l^4 \, \alpha \, (\alpha \, \gamma \, \theta)^{1/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \, \theta} - \frac{39.4784 \, l^2 \, x^2 \, \gamma \, (\alpha \, \gamma \, \theta)^{1/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \, \theta} - \\
 & \frac{39.4784 \, l^2 \, r^2 \, \theta \, (\alpha \, \gamma \, \theta)^{1/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \, \gamma} + \frac{893 \, 025. \, l^2 \, r^2 \, x^{16} \, \gamma^{16} \, \theta^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.25024 \times 10^7 \, l^2 \, r^3 \, x^{15} \, \gamma^{15} \, \theta^3 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.12653 \times 10^7 \, l^2 \, r^4 \, x^{14} \, \gamma^{14} \, \theta^4 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.25061 \times 10^8 \, l^2 \, r^5 \, x^{13} \, \gamma^{13} \, \theta^5 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.93918 \times 10^8 \, l^2 \, r^6 \, x^{12} \, \gamma^{12} \, \theta^6 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.78784 \times 10^9 \, l^2 \, r^7 \, x^{11} \, \gamma^{11} \, \theta^7 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{2.68175 \times 10^9 \, l^2 \, r^8 \, x^{10} \, \gamma^{10} \, \theta^8 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.06486 \times 10^9 \, l^2 \, r^9 \, x^9 \, \gamma^9 \, \theta^9 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{2.68175 \times 10^9 \, l^2 \, r^{10} \, x^8 \, \gamma^8 \, \theta^{10} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.78784 \times 10^9 \, l^2 \, r^{11} \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta^{11} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.93918 \times 10^8 \, l^2 \, r^{12} \, x^6 \, \gamma^6 \, \theta^{12} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.25061 \times 10^8 \, l^2 \, r^{13} \, x^5 \, \gamma^5 \, \theta^{13} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.12653 \times 10^7 \, l^2 \, r^{14} \, x^4 \, \gamma^4 \, \theta^{14} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.25024 \times 10^7 \, l^2 \, r^{15} \, x^3 \, \gamma^3 \, \theta^{15} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{893 \, 025. \, l^2 \, r^{16} \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 \, \theta^{16} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \, \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{11}} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{198\,450 \cdot l^2 r x^{15} \gamma^{15} \theta \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{6.44963 \times 10^6 l^2 r^2 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{6.21149 \times 10^7 l^2 r^3 x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^3 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{3.14543 \times 10^8 l^2 r^4 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{1.00634 \times 10^9 l^2 r^5 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^5 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{2.2146 \times 10^9 l^2 r^6 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{3.50363 \times 10^9 l^2 r^7 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^7 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{4.07338 \times 10^9 l^2 r^8 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{3.50363 \times 10^9 l^2 r^9 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^9 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{2.2146 \times 10^9 l^2 r^{10} x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^{10} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{1.00634 \times 10^9 l^2 r^{11} x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^{11} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{3.14543 \times 10^8 l^2 r^{12} x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{12} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{6.21149 \times 10^7 l^2 r^{13} x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{13} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{6.44963 \times 10^6 l^2 r^{14} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{14} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{198\,450 \cdot l^2 r^{15} x \gamma \theta^{15} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{11\,025 \cdot l^2 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} \\
 & \frac{945\,000 \cdot l^2 r x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \frac{1.65359 \times 10^7 l^2 r^2 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{198\,450 \cdot l^2 r^{15} x \gamma \theta^{15} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \frac{11\,025 \cdot l^2 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{4.90978 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^7 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \frac{1.31241 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{1.64412 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^9 \text{ x} \gamma \theta^9 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \frac{64710. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^{10} \theta^{10} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{48930. \text{l}^2 \text{ x}^8 \gamma^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \frac{804570. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^7 \gamma^7 \theta \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{4.33901 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \theta^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \frac{1.08978 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta^3 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{1.46288 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \frac{1.08978 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^5 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{4.33901 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} - \frac{804570. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x} \gamma \theta^7 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{48930. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \theta^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^6} + \frac{18921. \text{l}^2 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{195888. \text{l}^2 \text{ r x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \frac{656679. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{959424. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^3 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \frac{656679. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{195888. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x} \gamma \theta^5 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \frac{18921. \text{l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \theta^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{11875.2 \text{ l}^3 \text{ r x}^7 \gamma^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \frac{71251.3 \text{ l}^3 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^6 \gamma^5 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{178128. \text{ l}^3 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^5 \gamma^4 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{237504. \text{ l}^3 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^3 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{178128. \text{ l}^3 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x}^3 \gamma^2 \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{71251.3 \text{ l}^3 \text{ r}^6 \text{ x}^2 \gamma \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \frac{11875.2 \text{ l}^3 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x} \theta^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{3405. \text{ l}^2 \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} - \frac{19776. \text{ l}^2 \text{ r x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^4} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{34\,038. \, l^2 r^2 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \frac{19\,776. \, l^2 r^3 x \gamma \theta^3 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{3405. \, l^2 r^4 \theta^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \frac{26\,389.4 \, l^3 r x^5 \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{1319.47 \, l^3 x^6 \gamma^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{93\,682.3 \, l^3 r^2 x^4 \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{137\,225. \, l^3 r^3 x^3 \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{93\,682.3 \, l^3 r^4 x^2 \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \frac{26\,389.4 \, l^3 r^5 x \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{1319.47 \, l^3 r^6 \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{208. \, l^2 x^2 \gamma^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \frac{560. \, l^2 r x \gamma \theta \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{208. \, l^2 r^2 \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \frac{14\,891.1 \, l^3 r x^3 \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1884.96 \, l^3 x^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{26\,012.4 \, l^3 r^2 x^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \frac{14\,891.1 \, l^3 r^3 x \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1884.96 \, l^3 r^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{4. \, l^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^2} + \frac{1734.16 \, l^3 r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{640.885 \, l^3 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{640.885 \, l^3 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2)^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \frac{25.1327 \text{ l}^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)} \right) \right) / \left(\sqrt{-1. \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta + \text{r}^2 \theta^2 + \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\},$$

$$\left\{ \mathbf{c} \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{\left(-\frac{157.914 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r x} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{157.914 \text{ r x}^3 \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{39.4784 \text{ l}^4 \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\gamma \theta} + \frac{78.9568 \text{ l}^2 \text{x}^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \theta} - \frac{39.4784 \text{x}^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \theta} + \frac{78.9568 \text{l}^2 \text{r}^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \gamma} + \frac{236.871 \text{r}^2 \text{x}^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{157.914 \text{r}^3 \text{x} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{39.4784 \text{r}^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \gamma} + \frac{893\,025. \text{l}^2 \text{r}^2 \text{x}^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{1.07163 \times 10^7 \text{l}^2 \text{r}^3 \text{x}^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^3}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{5.89397 \times 10^7 \text{l}^2 \text{r}^4 \text{x}^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{1.96466 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 \text{r}^5 \text{x}^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^5}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{4.42047 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 \text{r}^6 \text{x}^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^6}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{7.07276 \times 10^8 \text{l}^2 \text{r}^7 \text{x}^9 \gamma^9 \theta^7}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} \right)} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{8.25155 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^8 \, x^8 \, \gamma^8 \, \theta^8}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{7.07276 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^9 \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta^9}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{4.42047 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{10} \, x^6 \, \gamma^6 \, \theta^{10}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.96466 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{11} \, x^5 \, \gamma^5 \, \theta^{11}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{5.89397 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{12} \, x^4 \, \gamma^4 \, \theta^{12}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.07163 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{13} \, x^3 \, \gamma^3 \, \theta^{13}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{893 \, 025. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{14} \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 \, \theta^{14}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{198 \, 450. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r \, x^{13} \, \gamma^{13} \, \theta}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{5.1597 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^2 \, x^{12} \, \gamma^{12} \, \theta^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.08807 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^3 \, x^{11} \, \gamma^{11} \, \theta^3}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.68683 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^4 \, x^{10} \, \gamma^{10} \, \theta^4}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.31629 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^5 \, x^9 \, \gamma^9 \, \theta^5}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{7.40615 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^6 \, x^8 \, \gamma^8 \, \theta^6}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{8.83499 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^7 \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta^7}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{7.40615 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^8 \, x^6 \, \gamma^6 \, \theta^8}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.31629 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^9 \, x^5 \, \gamma^5 \, \theta^9}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1.68683 \times 10^8 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^{10} x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{10}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.08807 \times 10^7 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^{11} x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{11}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{5.1597 \times 10^6 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^{12} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{12}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{198450. \mathfrak{l}^2 r^{13} x \gamma \theta^{13}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{11025. \mathfrak{l}^2 x^{12} \gamma^{12}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{724500. \mathfrak{l}^2 r x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{9.9162 \times 10^6 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^2 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{5.52069 \times 10^7 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^3 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^3}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.67985 \times 10^8 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^4 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^4}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.16021 \times 10^8 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^5 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^5}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{3.8808 \times 10^8 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^6 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^6}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.16021 \times 10^8 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^7 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^7}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.67985 \times 10^8 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^8 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^8}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{5.52069 \times 10^7 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^9 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^9}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{9.9162 \times 10^6 \mathfrak{l}^2 r^{10} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{10}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{724500. \mathfrak{l}^2 r^{11} x \gamma \theta^{11}}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^8} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{11\,025 \cdot l^2 r^{12} \theta^{12}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{31\,500 \cdot l^2 x^{10} \gamma^{10}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{975\,240 \cdot l^2 r x^9 \gamma^9 \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{8.48736 \times 10^6 l^2 r^2 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{3.29944 \times 10^7 l^2 r^3 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{7.04075 \times 10^7 l^2 r^4 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{8.99136 \times 10^7 l^2 r^5 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^5}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{7.04075 \times 10^7 l^2 r^6 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^6}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{3.29944 \times 10^7 l^2 r^7 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^7}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{8.48736 \times 10^6 l^2 r^8 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^8}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{975\,240 \cdot l^2 r^9 x \gamma \theta^9}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{31\,500 \cdot l^2 r^{10} \theta^{10}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{33\,210 \cdot l^2 x^8 \gamma^8}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{602\,460 \cdot l^2 r x^7 \gamma^7 \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{3.39863 \times 10^6 l^2 r^2 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{8.70372 \times 10^6 l^2 r^3 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^6} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1.17487 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^4 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^4}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{8.70372 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^5 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^5}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
& \frac{3.39863 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^6 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^6}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{602460. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^7 x \gamma \theta^7}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
& \frac{33210. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^8 \theta^8}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
& \frac{15720. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 x^6 \gamma^6}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{170670. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r x^5 \gamma^5 \theta}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{583320. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^2 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{856740. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^3 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^3}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{583320. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^4 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^4}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{170670. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^5 x \gamma \theta^5}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{15720. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^6 \theta^6}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{3201. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 x^4 \gamma^4}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{18816. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r x^3 \gamma^3 \theta}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{32526. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^2 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{18816. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 r^3 x \gamma \theta^3}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{3201. \text{l}^2 r^4 \theta^4}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 r x^5 \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{47500.9 \text{l}^3 r^2 x^4 \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{71251.3 \text{l}^3 r^3 x^3 \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{47500.9 \text{l}^3 r^4 x^2 \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 r^5 x \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{204. \text{l}^2 x^2 \gamma^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{552. \text{l}^2 r x \gamma \theta}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{204. \text{l}^2 r^2 \theta^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 r x^3 \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{1319.47 \text{l}^3 x^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{21111.5 \text{l}^3 r^2 x^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{11875.2 \text{l}^3 r^3 x \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{1319.47 \text{l}^3 r^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{4. \text{l}^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{1884.96 \text{l}^3 r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^2} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{565.487 \, l^3 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{565.487 \, l^3 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{201.062 \, l r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{25.1327 \, l^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma \theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{50.2655 \, l x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{50.2655 \, l r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{78.9568 \, l^2 r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha} + \frac{39.4784 \, l^4 \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta} - \\
 & \frac{39.4784 \, l^2 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \theta} - \\
 & \frac{39.4784 \, l^2 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \gamma} + \\
 & \frac{893025. \, l^2 r^2 x^{16} \gamma^{16} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.25024 \times 10^7 \, l^2 r^3 x^{15} \gamma^{15} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.12653 \times 10^7 \, l^2 r^4 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.25061 \times 10^8 \, l^2 r^5 x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.93918 \times 10^8 \, l^2 r^6 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.78784 \times 10^9 \, l^2 r^7 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{2.68175 \times 10^9 \, l^2 r^8 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{3.06486 \times 10^9 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^9 \text{ x}^9 \gamma^9 \theta^9 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{2.68175 \times 10^9 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{10} \text{ x}^8 \gamma^8 \theta^{10} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.78784 \times 10^9 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{11} \text{ x}^7 \gamma^7 \theta^{11} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.93918 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{12} \text{ x}^6 \gamma^6 \theta^{12} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.25061 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{13} \text{ x}^5 \gamma^5 \theta^{13} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.12653 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{14} \text{ x}^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{14} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.25024 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{15} \text{ x}^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{15} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{893\,025. \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^{16} \text{ x}^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{16} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{198\,450. \text{ l}^2 \text{ r x}^{15} \gamma^{15} \theta \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{6.44963 \times 10^6 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^2 \text{ x}^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{6.21149 \times 10^7 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^3 \text{ x}^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^3 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{3.14543 \times 10^8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^4 \text{ x}^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{1.00634 \times 10^9 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^5 \text{ x}^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^5 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{2.2146 \times 10^9 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^6 \text{ x}^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{3.50363 \times 10^9 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^7 \text{ x}^9 \gamma^9 \theta^7 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{4.07338 \times 10^9 \text{ l}^2 \text{ r}^8 \text{ x}^8 \gamma^8 \theta^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{x}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{r x} \gamma \theta - 1. \text{r}^2 \theta^2)^{10}} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{3.50363 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^9 \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta^9 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{2.2146 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{10} \, x^6 \, \gamma^6 \, \theta^{10} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.00634 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{11} \, x^5 \, \gamma^5 \, \theta^{11} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{3.14543 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{12} \, x^4 \, \gamma^4 \, \theta^{12} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{6.21149 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{13} \, x^3 \, \gamma^3 \, \theta^{13} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{6.44963 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{14} \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 \, \theta^{14} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{198450. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{15} \, x \, \gamma \, \theta^{15} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{11025. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, x^{14} \, \gamma^{14} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{945000. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r \, x^{13} \, \gamma^{13} \, \theta \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{1.65359 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^2 \, x^{12} \, \gamma^{12} \, \theta^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.16645 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^3 \, x^{11} \, \gamma^{11} \, \theta^3 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{4.56997 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^4 \, x^{10} \, \gamma^{10} \, \theta^4 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.13883 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^5 \, x^9 \, \gamma^9 \, \theta^5 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{1.92872 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^6 \, x^8 \, \gamma^8 \, \theta^6 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{2.2917 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^7 \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta^7 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{1.92872 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^8 \, x^6 \, \gamma^6 \, \theta^8 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1.13883 \times 10^9 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^9 \, x^5 \, \gamma^5 \, \theta^9 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.56997 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{10} \, x^4 \, \gamma^4 \, \theta^{10} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.16645 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{11} \, x^3 \, \gamma^3 \, \theta^{11} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{1.65359 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{12} \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 \, \theta^{12} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{945000. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{13} \, x \, \gamma \, \theta^{13} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{11025. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{14} \, \theta^{14} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{42525. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, x^{12} \, \gamma^{12} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.76274 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r \, x^{11} \, \gamma^{11} \, \theta \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{2.03855 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^2 \, x^{10} \, \gamma^{10} \, \theta^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.06151 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^3 \, x^9 \, \gamma^9 \, \theta^3 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.12868 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^4 \, x^8 \, \gamma^8 \, \theta^4 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{5.79744 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^5 \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta^5 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{7.08722 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^6 \, x^6 \, \gamma^6 \, \theta^6 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{5.79744 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^7 \, x^5 \, \gamma^5 \, \theta^7 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.12868 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^8 \, x^4 \, \gamma^4 \, \theta^8 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.06151 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^9 \, x^3 \, \gamma^3 \, \theta^9 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{2.03855 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{10} \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 \, \theta^{10} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} - \\
& \frac{1.76274 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{11} \, x \, \gamma \, \theta^{11} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} + \\
& \frac{42525. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{12} \, \theta^{12} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^8} + \\
& \frac{64710. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, x^{10} \, \gamma^{10} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{1.64412 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r \, x^9 \, \gamma^9 \, \theta \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} + \\
& \frac{1.31241 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^2 \, x^8 \, \gamma^8 \, \theta^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{4.90978 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^3 \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta^3 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} + \\
& \frac{1.02962 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^4 \, x^6 \, \gamma^6 \, \theta^4 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{1.30818 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^5 \, x^5 \, \gamma^5 \, \theta^5 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} + \\
& \frac{1.02962 \times 10^8 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^6 \, x^4 \, \gamma^4 \, \theta^6 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{4.90978 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^7 \, x^3 \, \gamma^3 \, \theta^7 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} + \\
& \frac{1.31241 \times 10^7 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^8 \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 \, \theta^8 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{1.64412 \times 10^6 \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^9 \, x \, \gamma \, \theta^9 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} + \\
& \frac{64710. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r^{10} \, \theta^{10} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^7} + \\
& \frac{48930. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, x^8 \, \gamma^8 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^6} - \\
& \frac{804570. \, \mathfrak{l}^2 \, r \, x^7 \, \gamma^7 \, \theta \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\mathfrak{l}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \, \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \, \gamma \, \theta - 1. \, r^2 \, \theta^2)^6} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{4.33901 \times 10^6 \, l^2 r^2 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.08978 \times 10^7 \, l^2 r^3 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^3 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{1.46288 \times 10^7 \, l^2 r^4 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.08978 \times 10^7 \, l^2 r^5 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^5 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{4.33901 \times 10^6 \, l^2 r^6 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{804570. \, l^2 r^7 x \gamma \theta^7 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{48930. \, l^2 r^8 \theta^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{18921. \, l^2 x^6 \gamma^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{195888. \, l^2 r x^5 \gamma^5 \theta \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{656679. \, l^2 r^2 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{959424. \, l^2 r^3 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^3 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{656679. \, l^2 r^4 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{195888. \, l^2 r^5 x \gamma \theta^5 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{18921. \, l^2 r^6 \theta^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{11875.2 \, l^3 r x^7 \gamma^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{71251.3 \, l^3 r^2 x^6 \gamma^5 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. r x \gamma \theta - 1. r^2 \theta^2)^5} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{178\,128 \cdot l^3 r^3 x^5 \gamma^4 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{237\,504 \cdot l^3 r^4 x^4 \gamma^3 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{178\,128 \cdot l^3 r^5 x^3 \gamma^2 \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{71\,251.3 l^3 r^6 x^2 \gamma \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{11\,875.2 l^3 r^7 x \theta^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{3405 \cdot l^2 x^4 \gamma^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{19\,776 \cdot l^2 r x^3 \gamma^3 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{34\,038 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{19\,776 \cdot l^2 r^3 x \gamma \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{3405 \cdot l^2 r^4 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{26\,389.4 l^3 r x^5 \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{1319.47 l^3 x^6 \gamma^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{93\,682.3 l^3 r^2 x^4 \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{137\,225 \cdot l^3 r^3 x^3 \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{93\,682.3 l^3 r^4 x^2 \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{26\,389.4 l^3 r^5 x \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1319.47 \, l^3 \, r^6 \, \theta^5 \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^4} + \\
 & \frac{208. \, l^2 \, x^2 \gamma^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} - \\
 & \frac{560. \, l^2 \, r \, x \gamma \theta \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} + \\
 & \frac{208. \, l^2 \, r^2 \theta^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} + \\
 & \frac{14891.1 \, l^3 \, r \, x^3 \gamma^2 \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1884.96 \, l^3 \, x^4 \gamma^3 \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} - \\
 & \frac{26012.4 \, l^3 \, r^2 \, x^2 \gamma \theta \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} + \\
 & \frac{14891.1 \, l^3 \, r^3 \, x \theta^2 \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1884.96 \, l^3 \, r^4 \theta^3 \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^3} + \\
 & \frac{4. \, l^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^2} + \\
 & \frac{1734.16 \, l^3 \, r \, x \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^2} - \\
 & \frac{640.885 \, l^3 \, x^2 \gamma \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^2} - \\
 & \frac{640.885 \, l^3 \, r^2 \theta \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)^2} - \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{25.1327 \, l^3 \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \, x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta - 1. \, r^2 \theta^2 \right)} \right) \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{-1. \, l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \, r \, x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \, \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \} \}
 \end{aligned}$$

In[]:= Manipulate[ContourPlot3D[

$$\left(\sqrt{\left(-\frac{157.91367041742973 \, l^2 \, r \, x \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{157.91367041742973 \, r \, x^3 \gamma^2 \, (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \right)} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{39.47841760435743 \cdot l^4 \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\gamma \theta} + \frac{78.95683520871486 \cdot l^2 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \theta} - \\
 & \frac{39.47841760435743 \cdot x^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \theta} + \frac{78.95683520871486 \cdot l^2 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \gamma} - \\
 & \frac{236.87050562614462 \cdot r^2 x^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} + \frac{157.91367041742973 \cdot r^3 x \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \\
 & \frac{39.47841760435743 \cdot r^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \gamma} - \frac{893025 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.07163 \cdot l^2 r^3 x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{5.893965 \cdot l^2 r^4 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.964655 \cdot l^2 r^5 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^5}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{4.42047375 \cdot l^2 r^6 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^6}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{7.072758 \cdot l^2 r^7 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^7}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{8.251551 \cdot l^2 r^8 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^8}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{7.072758 \cdot l^2 r^9 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^9}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{4.42047375 \cdot l^2 r^{10} x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^{10}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.964655 \cdot l^2 r^{11} x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^{11}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{5.893965 \cdot l^2 r^{12} x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{12}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.07163 \cdot l^2 r^{13} x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{13}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{893025 \cdot l^2 r^{14} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{14}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{198450 \cdot l^2 r x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{5.1597 \cdot *^6 l^2 r^2 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.08807 \cdot *^7 l^2 r^3 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.686825 \cdot *^8 l^2 r^4 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.3162875 \cdot *^8 l^2 r^5 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^5}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{7.406154 \cdot *^8 l^2 r^6 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^6}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{8.834994 \cdot *^8 l^2 r^7 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^7}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{7.406154 \cdot *^8 l^2 r^8 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^8}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.3162875 \cdot *^8 l^2 r^9 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^9}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.686825 \cdot *^8 l^2 r^{10} x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{10}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.08807 \cdot *^7 l^2 r^{11} x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{11}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{5.1597 \cdot *^6 l^2 r^{12} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{12}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{198450 \cdot l^2 r^{13} x \gamma \theta^{13}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{11025 \cdot l^2 x^{12} \gamma^{12}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{724500 \cdot l^2 r x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{9.9162 \cdot *^6 l^2 r^2 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{5.52069 \cdot l^2 r^3 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.67984775 \cdot l^2 r^4 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.160206 \cdot l^2 r^5 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^5}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{3.8808 \cdot l^2 r^6 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^6}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.160206 \cdot l^2 r^7 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^7}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.67984775 \cdot l^2 r^8 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^8}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{5.52069 \cdot l^2 r^9 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^9}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{9.9162 \cdot l^2 r^{10} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{10}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{724500 \cdot l^2 r^{11} x \gamma \theta^{11}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{11025 \cdot l^2 r^{12} \theta^{12}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{31500 \cdot l^2 x^{10} \gamma^{10}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{975240 \cdot l^2 r x^9 \gamma^9 \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{8.48736 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{3.299436 \cdot l^2 r^3 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{7.040754 \cdot l^2 r^4 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{8.99136 \cdot l^2 r^5 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^5}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{7.040754 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^6 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^6}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{3.299436 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^7 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^7}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{8.48736 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^8 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^8}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{975240. \text{`}\ l^2 r^9 x \gamma \theta^9}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{31500. \text{`}\ l^2 r^{10} \theta^{10}}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{33210. \text{`}\ l^2 x^8 \gamma^8}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{602460. \text{`}\ l^2 r x^7 \gamma^7 \theta}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{3.398625 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^2 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^2}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{8.70372 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^3 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^3}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.174869 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^4 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^4}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{8.70372 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^5 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^5}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{3.398625 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^6 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^6}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{602460. \text{`}\ l^2 r^7 x \gamma \theta^7}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{33210. \text{`}\ l^2 r^8 \theta^8}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{15720. \text{`}\ l^2 x^6 \gamma^6}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{170670. \text{`}\ l^2 r x^5 \gamma^5 \theta}{(\text{`}\ l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^5} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{583320 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{856740 \cdot l^2 r^3 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{583320 \cdot l^2 r^4 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{170670 \cdot l^2 r^5 x \gamma \theta^5}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{15720 \cdot l^2 r^6 \theta^6}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{3201 \cdot l^2 x^4 \gamma^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{18816 \cdot l^2 r x^3 \gamma^3 \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{32526 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{18816 \cdot l^2 r^3 x \gamma \theta^3}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{3201 \cdot l^2 r^4 \theta^4}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{11875.220230569419 \cdot l^3 r x^5 \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{47500.880922277676 \cdot l^3 r^2 x^4 \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{71251.3213834165 \cdot l^3 r^3 x^3 \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{47500.880922277676 \cdot l^3 r^4 x^2 \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{11875.220230569419 \cdot l^3 r^5 x \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{204 \cdot l^2 x^2 \gamma^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{552 \cdot l^2 r x \gamma \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{204 \cdot l^2 r^2 \theta^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{11875.220230569419 \cdot l^3 r x^3 \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{1319.4689145077132 \cdot l^3 x^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{21111.50263212341 \cdot l^3 r^2 x^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{11875.220230569419 \cdot l^3 r^3 x \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{1319.4689145077132 \cdot l^3 r^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{4 \cdot l^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{1884.9555921538758 \cdot l^3 r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{565.4866776461628 \cdot l^3 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{565.4866776461628 \cdot l^3 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{201.06192982974676 \cdot l r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{25.132741228718345 \cdot l^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma \theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{50.26548245743669 \cdot l x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{50.26548245743669 \cdot l r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{78.95683520871486 \cdot l^2 r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{39.47841760435743 \cdot l^4 \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta} - \\
 & \frac{39.47841760435743 \cdot l^2 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \theta} - \\
 & \frac{39.47841760435743 \cdot l^2 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \gamma} + \\
 & \frac{893025 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^{16} \gamma^{16} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.250235 \cdot 7 l^2 r^3 x^{15} \gamma^{15} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.1265275 \cdot 7 l^2 r^4 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.250611 \cdot 8 l^2 r^5 x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.93918025 \cdot 8 l^2 r^6 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.78783605 \cdot 9 l^2 r^7 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{2.681754075 \cdot 9 l^2 r^8 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.0648618 \cdot 9 l^2 r^9 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{2.681754075 \cdot 9 l^2 r^{10} x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{1.78783605 \cdot 9 l^2 r^{11} x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.93918025 \cdot 8 l^2 r^{12} x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{3.250611 \cdot 8 l^2 r^{13} x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{8.1265275 \cdot 7 l^2 r^{14} x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1.250235 \cdot \text{`}^7 \text{`}^2 r^{15} x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{15} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{893025. \cdot \text{`}^2 r^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{198450. \cdot \text{`}^2 r x^{15} \gamma^{15} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{6.449625 \cdot \text{`}^6 \text{`}^2 r^2 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{6.211485 \cdot \text{`}^7 \text{`}^2 r^3 x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{3.1454325 \cdot \text{`}^8 \text{`}^2 r^4 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{1.00633995 \cdot \text{`}^9 \text{`}^2 r^5 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{2.214602775 \cdot \text{`}^9 \text{`}^2 r^6 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{3.50363475 \cdot \text{`}^9 \text{`}^2 r^7 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{4.0733847 \cdot \text{`}^9 \text{`}^2 r^8 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{3.50363475 \cdot \text{`}^9 \text{`}^2 r^9 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{2.214602775 \cdot \text{`}^9 \text{`}^2 r^{10} x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{1.00633995 \cdot \text{`}^9 \text{`}^2 r^{11} x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{3.1454325 \cdot \text{`}^8 \text{`}^2 r^{12} x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
 & \frac{6.211485 \cdot \text{`}^7 \text{`}^2 r^{13} x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{6.449625 \cdot \text{`}^6 \text{`}^2 r^{14} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{198450 \cdot l^2 r^{15} x \gamma \theta^{15} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{11025 \cdot l^2 x^{14} \gamma^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{945000 \cdot l^2 r x^{13} \gamma^{13} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{1.6535925 \cdot 7 l^2 r^2 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.166445 \cdot 8 l^2 r^3 x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.56997275 \cdot 8 l^2 r^4 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.1388258 \cdot 9 l^2 r^5 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{1.928721375 \cdot 9 l^2 r^6 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{2.2917006 \cdot 9 l^2 r^7 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{1.928721375 \cdot 9 l^2 r^8 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.1388258 \cdot 9 l^2 r^9 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{4.56997275 \cdot 8 l^2 r^{10} x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.166445 \cdot 8 l^2 r^{11} x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{1.6535925 \cdot 7 l^2 r^{12} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{945000 \cdot l^2 r^{13} x \gamma \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{11025 \cdot l^2 r^{14} \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^9} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{42525 \cdot l^2 x^{12} \gamma^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.76274 \cdot \text{^}6 l^2 r x^{11} \gamma^{11} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{2.038554 \cdot \text{^}7 l^2 r^2 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.0615122 \cdot \text{^}8 l^2 r^3 x^9 \gamma^9 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.12868395 \cdot \text{^}8 l^2 r^4 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{5.7974364 \cdot \text{^}8 l^2 r^5 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{7.0872228 \cdot \text{^}8 l^2 r^6 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{5.7974364 \cdot \text{^}8 l^2 r^7 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{3.12868395 \cdot \text{^}8 l^2 r^8 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.0615122 \cdot \text{^}8 l^2 r^9 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{2.038554 \cdot \text{^}7 l^2 r^{10} x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.76274 \cdot \text{^}6 l^2 r^{11} x \gamma \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{42525 \cdot l^2 r^{12} \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{64710 \cdot l^2 x^{10} \gamma^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{1.64412 \cdot \text{^}6 l^2 r x^9 \gamma^9 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.3124115 \cdot \text{^}7 l^2 r^2 x^8 \gamma^8 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^7} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{4.909779 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^3 x^7 \gamma^7 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.02962295 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 8 \text{`}\ l^2 r^4 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{1.3081842 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 8 \text{`}\ l^2 r^5 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.02962295 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 8 \text{`}\ l^2 r^6 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{4.909779 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^7 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.3124115 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^8 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{1.64412 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^9 x \gamma \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{64710. \cdot \text{`}\wedge 2 \text{`}\ r^{10} \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{48930. \cdot \text{`}\wedge 2 \text{`}\ x^8 \gamma^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{804570. \cdot \text{`}\wedge 2 \text{`}\ r x^7 \gamma^7 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{4.339005 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^2 x^6 \gamma^6 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.089777 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^3 x^5 \gamma^5 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{1.462881 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^4 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.089777 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 7 \text{`}\ l^2 r^5 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{4.339005 \cdot \text{`}\wedge 6 \text{`}\ l^2 r^6 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{804570. \cdot \text{`}\wedge 2 \text{`}\ r^7 x \gamma \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(\text{`}\wedge 2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot \text{`}\ r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot \text{`}\ r^2 \theta^2)^6} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{48930 \cdot l^2 r^8 \theta^8 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{18921 \cdot l^2 x^6 \gamma^6 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{195888 \cdot l^2 r x^5 \gamma^5 \theta \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{656679 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^4 \gamma^4 \theta^2 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{959424 \cdot l^2 r^3 x^3 \gamma^3 \theta^3 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{656679 \cdot l^2 r^4 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^4 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{195888 \cdot l^2 r^5 x \gamma \theta^5 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{18921 \cdot l^2 r^6 \theta^6 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{11875.220230569419 \cdot l^3 r x^7 \gamma^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{71251.3213834165 \cdot l^3 r^2 x^6 \gamma^5 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{178128.30345854128 \cdot l^3 r^3 x^5 \gamma^4 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{237504.40461138837 \cdot l^3 r^4 x^4 \gamma^3 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{178128.30345854128 \cdot l^3 r^5 x^3 \gamma^2 \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{71251.3213834165 \cdot l^3 r^6 x^2 \gamma \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{11875.220230569419 \cdot l^3 r^7 x \theta^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{3405 \cdot l^2 x^4 \gamma^4 \sin[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{19776 \cdot l^2 r x^3 \gamma^3 \theta \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{34038 \cdot l^2 r^2 x^2 \gamma^2 \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{19776 \cdot l^2 r^3 x \gamma \theta^3 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{3405 \cdot l^2 r^4 \theta^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{26389.37829015426 \cdot l^3 r x^5 \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{1319.4689145077132 \cdot l^3 x^6 \gamma^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{93682.29293004764 \cdot l^3 r^2 x^4 \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{137224.76710880216 \cdot l^3 r^3 x^3 \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{93682.29293004764 \cdot l^3 r^4 x^2 \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{26389.37829015426 \cdot l^3 r^5 x \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{1319.4689145077132 \cdot l^3 r^6 \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{208 \cdot l^2 x^2 \gamma^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{560 \cdot l^2 r x \gamma \theta \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{208 \cdot l^2 r^2 \theta^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{14891.14917801562 \cdot l^3 r x^3 \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1884.9555921538758 \cdot l^3 x^4 \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1 \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1 \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{26012.387171723487 \cdot l^3 r^2 x^2 \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{14891.14917801562 \cdot l^3 r^3 x \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1884.9555921538758 \cdot l^3 r^4 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{4. \cdot l^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{1734.1591447815658 \cdot l^3 r x (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{640.8849013323178 \cdot l^3 x^2 \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{640.8849013323178 \cdot l^3 r^2 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \left. \frac{25.132741228718345 \cdot l^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta (l^2 \alpha^2 - 1. \cdot x^2 \gamma^2 + 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta - 1. \cdot r^2 \theta^2)} \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right), \{r, \\
 & 0, \\
 & 1\}, \{x, \\
 & 0, \\
 & 1\}, \{l, \\
 & 0, \\
 & 1\}], \{\alpha, 0, 2 \\
 & \pi\}, \{\theta, 0, 2 \\
 & \pi\}, \{\beta, 0, \pi / \\
 & 2\}, \{\gamma, 0, 2 \\
 & \pi\}]
 \end{aligned}$$

- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. l^2 r \times \text{ComplexInfinity}$ encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. r x^3 \text{ComplexInfinity}$ encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. l^4 \text{ComplexInfinity}$ encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{In[]:= Solve} & \left[\frac{2 \pi \sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}} - \right. \\
 & \left(- \frac{945 l^3 \alpha^2 (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{16 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{11/2}} + \right. \\
 & \frac{105 l^3 \alpha^2 \gamma \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
 & \frac{105 l^3 x \alpha^2 \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
 & \frac{105 l^3 \alpha^2 (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
 & \frac{105 l^3 \alpha^2 (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta) (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
 & \left. \frac{105 l^3 r \alpha^2 \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{105 l^3 r x \alpha^2 (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} + \\
 & \frac{105 l (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{16 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{9/2}} - \\
 & \frac{30 l^3 r x \alpha^2 \gamma \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l^3 \alpha^2 (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
 & \frac{15 l^3 \alpha^2 \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l^3 \alpha^2 \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
 & \frac{15 l \gamma \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
 & \frac{15 l^3 x \alpha^2 (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l x \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
 & \frac{15 l (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
 & \frac{15 l^3 r \alpha^2 (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
 & \frac{15 l (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta) (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{8 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \\
 & \frac{15 l r \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} - \frac{15 l r x (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta) (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{7/2}} + \\
 & \frac{3 l^3 \alpha^2}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \frac{6 l r x \gamma \theta}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \\
 & \frac{3 l (2 x \gamma - 4 r \theta) (-4 x \gamma + 2 r \theta)}{4 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \frac{3 l \theta (2 r x \gamma - 2 r^2 \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \\
 & \frac{3 l \gamma (-2 x^2 \gamma + 2 r x \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \frac{3 l x (-2 x \gamma^2 + 2 r \gamma \theta)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} + \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{3 l r (2 x \gamma \theta - 2 r \theta^2)}{2 (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{5/2}} - \frac{l}{(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2)^{3/2}} \right) \right) = \\
 & \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 + c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 c^2 r x \gamma \theta + c^2 r^2 \theta^2 + c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}, c]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Out}[*]= \left\{ \left\{ \mathbf{c} \rightarrow - \left(\left(1. \sqrt{\left(- \frac{3.16931 \times 10^{168} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
& \frac{3.16931 \times 10^{168} \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\gamma \theta} + \\
& \frac{1.58466 \times 10^{168} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \theta} - \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \theta} + \\
& \frac{1.58466 \times 10^{168} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \gamma} - \frac{4.75397 \times 10^{168} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} + \\
& \frac{3.16931 \times 10^{168} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \gamma} - \\
& \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{14} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{2.15075 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{13} \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.18291 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{12} \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{3.94304 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{11} \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{8.87184 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{10} \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{1.41949 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.65608 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{1.41949 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{8.87184 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{3.94304 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^{11}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.18291 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{2.15075 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^{13}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^{14}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma^{13} \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.03555 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{12} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{8.20471 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{11} \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{3.38544 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{10} \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{8.66274 \times 10^{174} \gamma^9 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.48641 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{1.77317 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.48641 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{8.66274 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{3.38544 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{8.20471 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^{11}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.03555 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^{13}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{1.45406 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{11} \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.99017 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{10} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{1.108 \times 10^{174} \gamma^9 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{3.37144 \times 10^{174} \gamma^8 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{6.3425 \times 10^{174} \gamma^7 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{7.78873 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{6.3425 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{3.37144 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{1.108 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.99017 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{1.45406 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^{11}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \theta^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{6.32202 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.9573 \times 10^{172} \gamma^9 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{1.7034 \times 10^{173} \gamma^8 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{6.62193 \times 10^{173} \gamma^7 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{1.41307 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.80456 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{1.41307 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{6.62193 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{1.7034 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.9573 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{6.32202 \times 10^{170} \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{6.66521 \times 10^{170} \gamma^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{1.20913 \times 10^{172} \gamma^7 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{6.82101 \times 10^{172} \gamma^6 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{1.74683 \times 10^{173} \gamma^5 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{2.35795 \times 10^{173} \gamma^4 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{1.74683 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{6.82101 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{1.20913 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{6.66521 \times 10^{170} \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{3.15499 \times 10^{170} \gamma^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{3.42533 \times 10^{171} \gamma^5 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{1.17072 \times 10^{172} \gamma^4 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{1.71947 \times 10^{172} \gamma^3 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{1.17072 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{3.42533 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{3.15499 \times 10^{170} \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
 & \frac{6.42438 \times 10^{169} \gamma^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{3.77635 \times 10^{170} \gamma^3 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{6.52794 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{3.77635 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{6.42438 \times 10^{169} \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{9.53338 \times 10^{170} \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{1.43001 \times 10^{171} \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{9.53338 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{4.09426 \times 10^{168} \gamma^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{1.10786 \times 10^{169} \gamma \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{4.09426 \times 10^{168} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{4.23706 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{2.22168 \times 10^{154} \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \frac{1.11084 \times 10^{154} \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{8.02797 \times 10^{166}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \frac{3.78309 \times 10^{169} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{1.13493 \times 10^{169} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} + \frac{1.13493 \times 10^{169} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{1.16572 \times 10^{154} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \frac{1.11084 \times 10^{154} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{4.0353 \times 10^{168} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \frac{5.04412 \times 10^{167} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma \theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{1.00882 \times 10^{168} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \frac{1.00882 \times 10^{168} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{1.58466 \times 10^{168} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha} + \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta} - \\
 & \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \theta} - \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \gamma} + \\
 & \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{16} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{2.50921 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{15} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{1.63098 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{14} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{6.52394 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{13} \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{1.79408 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{12} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{3.58817 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{11} \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{5.38225 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{10} \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{6.15114 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{5.38225 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{3.58817 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{1.79408 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{6.52394 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{1.63098 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{2.50921 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^{15} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \\
 & \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma^{15} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
 & \frac{1.29443 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{14} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{1.24664 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{13} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{6.31285 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{12} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{2.01971 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{11} \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{4.44468 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{10} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{7.03176 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{8.17524 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{7.03176 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{4.44468 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{2.01971 \times 10^{175} \gamma^5 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{6.31285 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{1.24664 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{1.29443 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^{15} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \frac{1.8966 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{13} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{3.31874 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{12} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \frac{2.34104 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{11} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{9.17189 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{10} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \frac{2.28561 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{3.87092 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \frac{4.59942 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{3.87092 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \frac{2.28561 \times 10^{175} \gamma^5 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{9.17189 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \frac{2.34104 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{3.31874 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \frac{1.8966 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{8.53472 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
& \frac{3.5378 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{11} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{4.09136 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{10} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
& \frac{2.13044 \times 10^{174} \gamma^9 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{6.27924 \times 10^{174} \gamma^8 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1.16354 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{1.4224 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.16354 \times 10^{175} \gamma^5 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{6.27924 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{2.13044 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{4.09136 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{3.5378 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{8.53472 \times 10^{170} \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{1.29872 \times 10^{171} \gamma^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{3.29973 \times 10^{172} \gamma^9 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{2.634 \times 10^{173} \gamma^8 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{9.85388 \times 10^{173} \gamma^7 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{2.06644 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{2.62551 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{2.06644 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{9.85388 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{2.634 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{3.29973 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{1.29872 \times 10^{171} \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{9.8202 \times 10^{170} \gamma^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.61476 \times 10^{172} \gamma^7 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{8.70834 \times 10^{172} \gamma^6 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{2.18717 \times 10^{173} \gamma^5 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{2.93599 \times 10^{173} \gamma^4 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{2.18717 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{8.70834 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
 & \frac{1.61476 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{9.8202 \times 10^{170} \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
 & \frac{3.79743 \times 10^{170} \gamma^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{3.93145 \times 10^{171} \gamma^5 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
 & \frac{1.31795 \times 10^{172} \gamma^4 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{1.92555 \times 10^{172} \gamma^3 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1.31795 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{3.93145 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{3.79743 \times 10^{170} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{2.38334 \times 10^{170} \gamma^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{1.43001 \times 10^{171} \gamma^5 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{3.57502 \times 10^{171} \gamma^4 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{4.76669 \times 10^{171} \gamma^3 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{3.57502 \times 10^{171} \gamma^2 \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{1.43001 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{2.38334 \times 10^{170} \theta^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{6.8338 \times 10^{169} \gamma^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{3.96902 \times 10^{170} \gamma^3 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{6.83139 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{3.96902 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{6.8338 \times 10^{169} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{5.29632 \times 10^{170} \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \gamma^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{1.88019 \times 10^{171} \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{2.75409 \times 10^{171} \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{1.88019 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{5.29632 \times 10^{170} \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{4.17454 \times 10^{168} \gamma^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
& \frac{1.12391 \times 10^{169} \gamma \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{4.17454 \times 10^{168} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \\
& \frac{2.98864 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \frac{3.78309 \times 10^{169} \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
& \frac{5.22066 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{2.98864 \times 10^{170} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
& \frac{3.78309 \times 10^{169} \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{8.02797 \times 10^{166} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\left. \left(\sqrt{\left(-2.00699 \times 10^{166} \alpha^2 + 2.00699 \times 10^{166} \gamma^2 - 4.01398 \times 10^{166} \gamma \theta + 2.00699 \times 10^{166} \theta^2 + 2.00699 \times 10^{166} \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)} \right) \right\} ,$$

$$\left\{ \mathbf{c} \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{\left(-\frac{3.16931 \times 10^{168} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{3.16931 \times 10^{168} \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\gamma \theta} + \frac{1.58466 \times 10^{168} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \theta} - \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \theta} + \frac{1.58466 \times 10^{168} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha \gamma} - \frac{4.75397 \times 10^{168} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} + \frac{3.16931 \times 10^{168} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3} - \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha^3 \gamma} - \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{14} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{2.15075 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{13} \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{1.18291 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{12} \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{3.94304 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{11} \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \frac{8.87184 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{10} \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \right)} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1.41949 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.65608 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{1.41949 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{8.87184 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{3.94304 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^{11}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.18291 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{2.15075 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^{13}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} - \\
& \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^{14}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \\
& \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma^{13} \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.03555 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{12} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{8.20471 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{11} \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{3.38544 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{10} \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{8.66274 \times 10^{174} \gamma^9 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.48641 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
& \frac{1.77317 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
& \frac{1.48641 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{8.66274 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{3.38544 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{8.20471 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^{11}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.03555 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^{13}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{1.45406 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{11} \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{1.99017 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{10} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{1.108 \times 10^{174} \gamma^9 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{3.37144 \times 10^{174} \gamma^8 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{6.3425 \times 10^{174} \gamma^7 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{7.78873 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{6.3425 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{3.37144 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{1.108 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{1.99017 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{1.45406 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^{11}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \theta^{12}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \\
 & \frac{6.32202 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{1.9573 \times 10^{172} \gamma^9 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{1.7034 \times 10^{173} \gamma^8 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{6.62193 \times 10^{173} \gamma^7 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1.41307 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{1.80456 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{1.41307 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{6.62193 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{1.7034 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{1.9573 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^9}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
& \frac{6.32202 \times 10^{170} \theta^{10}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \frac{6.66521 \times 10^{170} \gamma^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{1.20913 \times 10^{172} \gamma^7 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{6.82101 \times 10^{172} \gamma^6 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{1.74683 \times 10^{173} \gamma^5 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{2.35795 \times 10^{173} \gamma^4 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{1.74683 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{6.82101 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{1.20913 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^7}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{6.66521 \times 10^{170} \theta^8}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \\
& \frac{3.15499 \times 10^{170} \gamma^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{3.42533 \times 10^{171} \gamma^5 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{1.17072 \times 10^{172} \gamma^4 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{1.71947 \times 10^{172} \gamma^3 \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{1.17072 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{3.42533 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^5}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{3.15499 \times 10^{170} \theta^6}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{6.42438 \times 10^{169} \gamma^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{3.77635 \times 10^{170} \gamma^3 \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{6.52794 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \\
& \frac{3.77635 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta^3}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{6.42438 \times 10^{169} \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{9.53338 \times 10^{170} \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{1.43001 \times 10^{171} \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{9.53338 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{1.43001 \times 10^{171} \theta^4}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{4.09426 \times 10^{168} \gamma^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{1.10786 \times 10^{169} \gamma \theta}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \frac{4.09426 \times 10^{168} \theta^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{4.23706 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \frac{2.38335 \times 10^{170} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{2.22168 \times 10^{154} \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1.11084 \times 10^{154} \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \frac{8.02797 \times 10^{166}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{3.78309 \times 10^{169} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} + \frac{1.13493 \times 10^{169} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{1.13493 \times 10^{169} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \frac{1.16572 \times 10^{154} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \frac{1.11084 \times 10^{154} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} + \frac{4.0353 \times 10^{168} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{5.04412 \times 10^{167} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\gamma \theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \frac{1.00882 \times 10^{168} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \\
 & \frac{1.00882 \times 10^{168} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}{\alpha^2 \gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} + \frac{1.58466 \times 10^{168} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha} + \\
 & \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta} - \\
 & \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \theta} - \\
 & \frac{7.92328 \times 10^{167} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\alpha \gamma} + \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{16} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{2.50921 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{15} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \frac{1.63098 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{14} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} - \\
 & \frac{6.52394 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{13} \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \frac{1.79408 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{12} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{3.58817 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{11} \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \frac{5.38225 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{10} \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} \\
& \frac{6.15114 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \frac{5.38225 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} \\
& \frac{3.58817 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \frac{1.79408 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} \\
& \frac{6.52394 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \frac{1.63098 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} \\
& \frac{2.50921 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^{15} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} + \frac{1.79229 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{11}} \\
& \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma^{15} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{1.29443 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{14} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \\
& \frac{1.24664 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{13} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{6.31285 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{12} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \\
& \frac{2.01971 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{11} \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{4.44468 \times 10^{175} \gamma^{10} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \\
& \frac{7.03176 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{8.17524 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \\
& \frac{7.03176 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{4.44468 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \\
& \frac{2.01971 \times 10^{175} \gamma^5 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{6.31285 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \\
& \frac{1.24664 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{1.29443 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} \\
& \frac{3.98287 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^{15} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^{10}} + \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} \\
& \frac{1.8966 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{13} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{3.31874 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{12} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} \\
& \frac{2.34104 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{11} \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{9.17189 \times 10^{174} \gamma^{10} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} \\
& \frac{2.28561 \times 10^{175} \gamma^9 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{3.87092 \times 10^{175} \gamma^8 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{4.59942 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{3.87092 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{2.28561 \times 10^{175} \gamma^5 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{9.17189 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{2.34104 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{3.31874 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} - \\
 & \frac{1.8966 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^{13} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \frac{2.21271 \times 10^{170} \theta^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^9} + \\
 & \frac{8.53472 \times 10^{170} \gamma^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{3.5378 \times 10^{172} \gamma^{11} \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{4.09136 \times 10^{173} \gamma^{10} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{2.13044 \times 10^{174} \gamma^9 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{6.27924 \times 10^{174} \gamma^8 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{1.16354 \times 10^{175} \gamma^7 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{1.4224 \times 10^{175} \gamma^6 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{1.16354 \times 10^{175} \gamma^5 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{6.27924 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{2.13044 \times 10^{174} \gamma^3 \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{4.09136 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} - \frac{3.5378 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^{11} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \\
 & \frac{8.53472 \times 10^{170} \theta^{12} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^8} + \frac{1.29872 \times 10^{171} \gamma^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{3.29973 \times 10^{172} \gamma^9 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{2.634 \times 10^{173} \gamma^8 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{9.85388 \times 10^{173} \gamma^7 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{2.06644 \times 10^{174} \gamma^6 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{2.62551 \times 10^{174} \gamma^5 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{2.06644 \times 10^{174} \gamma^4 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{9.85388 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{2.634 \times 10^{173} \gamma^2 \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} - \\
 & \frac{3.29973 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{1.29872 \times 10^{171} \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \\
 & \frac{3.29973 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^9 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} + \frac{1.29872 \times 10^{171} \theta^{10} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^7} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{9.8202 \times 10^{170} \gamma^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{1.61476 \times 10^{172} \gamma^7 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{8.70834 \times 10^{172} \gamma^6 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{2.18717 \times 10^{173} \gamma^5 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{2.93599 \times 10^{173} \gamma^4 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{2.18717 \times 10^{173} \gamma^3 \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{8.70834 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} - \frac{1.61476 \times 10^{172} \gamma \theta^7 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \\
& \frac{9.8202 \times 10^{170} \theta^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^6} + \frac{3.79743 \times 10^{170} \gamma^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{3.93145 \times 10^{171} \gamma^5 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{1.31795 \times 10^{172} \gamma^4 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{1.92555 \times 10^{172} \gamma^3 \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{1.31795 \times 10^{172} \gamma^2 \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{3.93145 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{3.79743 \times 10^{170} \theta^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{2.38334 \times 10^{170} \gamma^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \frac{1.43001 \times 10^{171} \gamma^5 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{3.57502 \times 10^{171} \gamma^4 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{4.76669 \times 10^{171} \gamma^3 \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{3.57502 \times 10^{171} \gamma^2 \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} - \\
& \frac{1.43001 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \\
& \frac{2.38334 \times 10^{170} \theta^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^5} + \frac{6.8338 \times 10^{169} \gamma^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{3.96902 \times 10^{170} \gamma^3 \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{6.83139 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
& \frac{3.96902 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{6.8338 \times 10^{169} \theta^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{5.29632 \times 10^{170} \gamma^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \gamma^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{1.88019 \times 10^{171} \gamma^3 \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \\
 & \frac{2.75409 \times 10^{171} \gamma^2 \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{1.88019 \times 10^{171} \gamma \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{5.29632 \times 10^{170} \theta^4 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} - \\
 & \frac{2.64816 \times 10^{169} \theta^5 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^4} + \frac{4.17454 \times 10^{168} \gamma^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{1.12391 \times 10^{169} \gamma \theta \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{4.17454 \times 10^{168} \theta^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \\
 & \frac{2.98864 \times 10^{170} \gamma^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \frac{3.78309 \times 10^{169} \gamma^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{5.22066 \times 10^{170} \gamma \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{2.98864 \times 10^{170} \theta^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} - \\
 & \frac{3.78309 \times 10^{169} \theta^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^3} + \frac{8.02797 \times 10^{166} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} + \\
 & \frac{3.48044 \times 10^{169} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{(1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \frac{1.28625 \times 10^{169} \gamma (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \\
 & \left. \left. \left. \frac{1.28625 \times 10^{169} \theta (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)^2} - \frac{5.04412 \times 10^{167} (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{\gamma \theta (1. \alpha^2 - 1. \gamma^2 + 2. \gamma \theta - 1. \theta^2)} \right) \right) \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{(-2.00699 \times 10^{166} \alpha^2 + 2.00699 \times 10^{166} \gamma^2 - 4.01398 \times 10^{166} \gamma \theta + \right. \\
 & \left. 2.00699 \times 10^{166} \theta^2 + 2.00699 \times 10^{166} \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right) \left. \right) \left. \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$